

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE AND TEAMS PROCESSES TOWARD DECISION MAKING AT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN TERNATE MUNICIPALITY

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to know the effect of organizational structure and teams processes toward decision making of elementary school principals in Ternate Municipality. This study consisted of two exogenous variable, they are organizational structure and endogenous variable is decision making of elementary schools principals. The population of this study was all of the elementary school principals in Ternate, they were 100 respondents. The sample was taken by applying simple random sampling. The total sample of this study was 80 principals. The result of study showed that, (1) There is a significant direct effect of organizational structure toward decision making.(2) There is a significant direct effect of team processes toward decision making. (3) There is a significant direct effect of organizational structure toward team processes. Based on the result of this study, the researcher suggested to the principals in order to improve the organizational structure and team processes in school organization so they could make decision effectively, and finally the school goal achieved.

Keywords: Decision making, organizational structure, team processes.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a very important and strategic factor in national development, which is oriented towards improving the quality of human resources. Education is a process of transforming cultural values as inheritance of values from generation to generation. RI Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning National Education System article 4 paragraph (3) that education is held as a process of civilizing and empowering students that lasts for life. Education is also expected to foster the ability to deal with current and future demands, both changes internally and externally in educational institutions. Specifically, internal changes in educational institutions are with the quality of educational organizations through strategic management in improving the quality of education, namely: expected vision and mission and organizational goals. While externally there is an interaction between the organization and the environment, both when receiving input, process implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Leadership is a very important and strategic factor in carrying out its role in the organization. Various researches have proven that leader factors play an important role in the development and progress of an organization. Schools as educational institutions which include non-profit institutions are also inseparable from this phenomenon, which is why in many cases educational

institutions, especially the leadership level, must know the various expectations and needs of stakeholders. Reality shows that, education has not fully given enlightenment to society through the value of benefits. This condition is proven by the low quality of graduates. Therefore, to prepare human resources through education as successors, it has not met the expectations of the people and is more ironic about the occurrence of a moral crisis as a civilized, civilized, and dignified nation.

Principals are top leaders, have a very strategic role, not only increase their responsibility and leadership authority in school programs, but have overall responsibility for changes and progress of school organizations including decision making, organizational structure, and the implementation of an effective process team. The problem that arises in the current leadership of the principal is that there is no attempt to dynamically increase the professionalism of managerial leadership, and that focusing on the needs of the abilities and skills acquired is still natural through the experience process. Lack of specific training on management of school-based management. Do not understand the management level and skills needed by the principal, namely conceptual skills (conceptual skills), human skills (human skills), and technical skills (technical skills). While the demands of the modern education world today are in need of a leader who has strategic managerial insight, where the results achieved lead to customer satisfaction, cost efficiency, prioritizing the learning process, school development and managerial leadership of the principal. Realizing this, the principal was confronted with various challenges to change and the development of education in a planned, directed and sustainable manner to improve the quality of education. On the other hand, the quality of school principals as managers is strongly influenced by performance (performance), in decision making efforts, designing organizational structures, and implementing process team formation. Decision Making is the process of producing and choosing from a set of choices to solve a problem. Decision making in general is the act of choosing one choice among a set of choices. The decision-making process includes: recognizing and defining decision situations, identifying choices, choosing the best choices, and implementing those decisions. Mukhneri (2011: 150) "decision making is a daily work that must be carried out by the leader and by the implementers in the field, because the organization or school is faced with problems that continue to emerge as a logical consequence of a continuous change, along with the demands of change in the community" . Furthermore, Invancevic, Konapake and Matteson (2008: 392-395) decision making are influenced by several aspects including: (1) values, namely references and beliefs used by a person when faced with a situation where choices must be made, (2) attitude towards risk, people with the type of risk lovers (risk lovers) and risk averse (risk averse) will have different decisions on a problem, (3) potential interference, where every decision can potentially cause interference, so that it will be a decision making decision, (4) escalation of commitment, namely increasing commitment to previous decisions to avoid failures in decisions that have already been made. Decision-making is to identify and choose solutions to lead to the expected outcome. This means that the process starts with a problem and ends when the solution has been chosen. The quality of decision making in an organization depends on choosing the right destination and identifying the tools to

achieve it. Decision making is closely related to the organizational structure. Organizational structure, clearly describing the separation of work activities from one another and how activity and function relationships are restricted. A good organizational structure must explain the relationship of authority who reports to whom. This means that the organizational structure is a pattern of relationships between positions within the organization and between members in the organization. In management science, organizing is the process of making organizational structures. The process is important and has a purpose, including the workers can do the work effectively and efficiently. The management process will later create an organizational structure, to determine how tasks will be shared and resources will be deployed. Richard L.Dafft (2010: 245) Organizational structure as a framework in which an organization determines how to divide tasks, use resources, and coordinate departments. Organizational structure is a formal framework in which tasks and jobs are divided, grouped and coordinated. When a leader designs an organization in the organizational structure process, as a key element includes: work specialization, departmentalization, chain of command, range of control, centralization and formalization.

Colquitt (2009: 371) Decision making and organizational structure cannot be separated from the effectiveness of teams in an organization, especially the process team. The process team (Teams Processes) are various types of activities and interactions that occur in teams that contribute to the ultimate goal. Team formation in organizations is a very important factor. Because the team is a group of people who work together, interact, and have a commitment to achieve common goals. While team effectiveness is a process that includes members' commitment to achieving a common goal. Robbins and Judge (2009: 361) "An effective team has a general goal that provides direction, momentum and commitment of its members, while a successful team is a team that transforms general goals into realistic, measurable and specific performance goals." formed from groups consisting of individuals where each individual has a recognized and valued contribution and is motivated to work in the same direction to get clarity, understanding, and achieve goals, which is the responsibility of the team. The process team was formed to create high-performance organizations, it was stated that the difference between work groups and teams was related to performance. A well-formed team can direct, self-regulate and have their own autonomy. The formation of a process team, when a number of people have a common goal and recognize that personal success depends on the success of others in the team. The process team is also a small group with members who depend on each other with high interdependency, coordinated, commitment, effective, and synergistic to achieve a goal in the organization. The problems faced by principals and teachers and education staff today in general, and especially Kota Ternate Public Elementary School show that, still low managerial competence leadership in decision making, administrative management and organizational structure management and process teams are not optimal. These factors cause low quality of education. Thus, the strategic role of this research is to find out whether the organizational structure and process team influence the decision making of principals in Ternate City State Primary School. This is very interesting to be studied and

studied further to achieve organizational goals that are expected to be accompanied by supporting theories.

1. Decision Making (Decision Making)

Decision making is the process of choosing one choice among a set of choices. Decision making is basically the process of determining the right choices to serve as a basis for problem solving in an effort to achieve goals. Colquitt (2009: 256) suggests that "decision making is a process of generating and selecting from alternatives to solve a problem." Decision making is the process of selecting and producing a set of choices to solve a problem. Decision making is one of the most important factors for a leader in an organization. Because in leadership organizations faced with various problems, both internally and externally. Decision making is also a strategic tool for a leader in acting to choose, develop and assess an alternative in order to solve problems. Schermerhorn (2011: 206) "Decision making is the process of choices a course of action to deal with a problem or opportunity." Decision making is the process of choosing actions to solve problems. Decision making is the most important part of a job. This looks like a leader decides how employees should be given specific duties and responsibilities in the organization. Decision making is also part of the activities of a leader to solve problems in an effort to achieve organizational goals. In the decision-making process, an important criterion for solving problems is the need to identify problems. This means that a leader must determine the relevant conditions in making a decision. Kreitner and Kinicki (2010: 336) "Decision making entails identifying and choices of alternative solutions to the desired state of affairs." Decision making requires identification and selecting alternative choices that lead to desired goals. Decision making is the basis for organizational behavior to achieve the expected goals. Therefore, as leaders must have awareness in the decision making process. Mcaneane and Glinow (2010: 198) that "decision making is a conscious process of making choices among people with the intention of moving toward some desired state of affairs." Decision making is a process of awareness to make one of the choices among other alternatives towards several desired goals.

In the science of management decision making consists of the decision to make choices and actions (chooice and action decisions) and problem solving decisions based on programmed decisions and non-programmed decisions. In decision making is divided into two types of decisions namely programmed decisions and decisions that are not programmed. Dafft (2010: 214), mentions that: Programmed decision, a decision made in response to a situation that is often enough to enable decision rules to be developed and applied in the future, while Non-programmed decision, a decision made in response to a situation that is unique, is poorly defined and largely unstructured, and has important consequences for the organization. "Programmed decision making is a decision taken to answer situations that often arise so that the provisions in making decisions can be made and applied, while unprogrammed decisions are decisions taken to respond to situations that are unique, difficult to recognize, and highly unstructured, and have important consequences for the organization. here are five steps in the decision making process,

namely: (1) identifying problems, (2) evaluating alternatives, (3) choosing actions and behaviors, (4) implementing decisions, and (5) evaluating results. John R. Schermerhorn (2010: 162) five stages of the decision making process (1) identify and define the problem, (2) generate and evaluate alternative solutions, (3) choose a preferred course of action and conduct the ethics double check, (4) implement the decision and (5) evaluate result”

In the science of decision-making process management there are many models used by leaders to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization. Invancevich, Konapaske, and Matteson (2008: 38) have three models in decision making, namely: (a) rational decision making processes, (b) alternatives to rational decision making: administrative decision making, bounded rationality approach, (c) intuitive decision making . It can be explained that the decision making process includes: rational models, rational bound alternative models include: bound administrative and rational decision making and intuition models. In educational institutions, the decision-making process carried out by leaders generally uses administrative and strategic decision-making models. Both of these decision models are priority and operational decisions and have strategic steps in efforts to achieve organizational goals. Mukhneri Mukhtar (2011: 181) stated that "Administrative decisions are decisions taken routinely related to daily tasks in the organization or school and are short-term related to various internal factors that can be controlled by their implementation. While strategic decisions are decisions that are more related to external factors of the organization, for the sake of long-term interests and usually cannot be monitored directly by the organization. Kreitner and Kinicki (2010: 347) there are four styles in decision making, namely: (1) directive style, (2) analytic style, (3) conceptual style, and (4) behavioral style. Ability to make decisions quickly, good and high quality is an important skill for a leader in the organization. The quality of decision making in an organization depends on choosing the right destination and identifying the tools to achieve it. With good integration between behavioral and structural factors that can improve high-quality decisions.

2. Organizational Structure Organizational

structure is a set of elements that can be used in an organization. The organizational structure is also a structured pattern that complements an organization with its elements. The organizational structure shows how work and tasks are separated and coordinated between individuals and groups within an organization. Dafft (2010: 244) "The frame work in which the organization defines how tasks are devided, resources are deployed, and tasks are coordinated." Organizational structure as an organizational framework, how tasks are shared, resources are deployed, and coordination is department. Next John R. Schermerhorn (2010: 238-239) "The systems of tasks, workflows, reporting, relationships, and communications channels that link together the work of diverse individuals and groups." The organizational structure is a system of tasks, workflows, reporting, and communication that has a common goal for individuals and groups in one organization. The organizational structure is a conception of the relationship between individuals and groups in work internally and externally. Gibson et. al (2006: 395) argues that "The processes by which they make choices are

termed organization design, which means quite simple decisions and actions that result in organizational structure." A process carried out by the leadership in making choices for designing organization, and is a decision and action that results in an organizational structure. Furthermore Colquitt (2009: 517) "The Organizational Structure Formally Dictates how jobs and tasks are devided and coordinated between individuals and groups within the company." Organizational structures formally show how work and tasks are separated and coordinated between individuals and groups within the organization. This is important for the leadership to place "the right man on the right place," namely the division of work and authority in accordance with their expertise, in order to support the achievement of organizational goals. In relation to the organizational structure, leaders must know and pay attention to several dimensions that are very important in the organization, namely work specialization, departmentalization, chain of command, range of control, centralization, and formalization. Invancevic, Konapaske, and Matteson (2008: 451) have four parts in the organizational structure, namely the division of labor, authority, division of department, and span of control. The division of work is the detail of work assignments for each individual in the organization, to be responsible and carry out their respective duties. In the division of work tasks by the leadership of the subordinates must be professionally based on the analysis of the needs, expertise and scientific specifications they have, in order to realize the goals of the organization effectively and efficiently.

McShane and Glinow (2010: 390) state that, organizational structure elements include: (a) Span of control, (b) centralization, (c) decentralization, and (d) formalization. Centralization and decentralization relate to the hierarchy level where decisions are made. Centralization is an authority in making decisions held by the highest position in organizational size. Centralization relates to the process of decision-making authority in organizational structures. While decentralization is an authority in decision-making derived at a lower level. In the organizational structure, formalization is a process of achieving the objectives of a work formalized in writing, so that each member of the organization can know officially about the assignments and work given to be carried out based on the statutes of the organization. Furthermore, the structure of socialization is also influenced by contingency factors in the organization.

Robbins and Coulter (2009: 247) state that there are four contingency factors that affect the organizational structure, namely: (1) strategy and structure, 2) size and structure, 3) technology and structure, and (4) uncertainty about the environment and structure Organizational structure is a formal way of dividing, grouping and coordinating tasks. The division and grouping of tasks that are in accordance with the skills and expertise and interests of members will increase the members' ties to work in the organization effectively and efficiently. The organizational structure aims to regulate or reduce uncertainty about employee behavior. The organizational structure gives freedom to members of the organization to work in accordance with their expertise. On the other hand the organizational structure provides delegation, authority and tasks to organizational members in certain positions within the organization.

3. Process Team (Team Processes)

Process teams are various types of activities and interactions that occur in teams that contribute to the final goal. The team as a collection of several individuals who conduct an interaction activity, influence each other, dependence, collective cooperation, and have a commitment to achieve a goal. Schermerhorn (2011: 157) "The team is a group of people holding themselves collectively accountable for using complimentary skills to achieve a common purpose". It can be explained that the team is a group of people who are collectively responsible for achieving common goals. McShane and Glinow (2008: 234) suggested that; The groups of two or more people who interact and influence each other, are mutually accountable for common goals associated with organizational objectives, and perceive themselves as a social entity within an organization. Teams are groups that consist of two people or more interact and influence each other, are responsible for achieving common goals related to organizational goals and consider themselves as social entities in an organization. In organizations between team members interdependence means that in carrying out the work activities the team members need each other to complete the tasks that are their responsibility, as a commitment to achieve the goals.

Kreitner and Kinicki (2008: 306), stated that "The team of small group with complementary skills who hold themselves mutually accountable for common purpose goals, and approaches". It can be explained that the team is a small group with the complementary skills of mutual restraint responsible for the same purpose. Team definition has three very basic components, namely the existence of two or more people, carrying out regular interactions, and having a common goal. Gary Yukl (2001: 366) suggests that "The team said, referring to a small task group where the members have same goal, the role of the interdependent and complementary skills. "The team refers to a small task group whose members share the same goals, interdependent roles and complementary skills. A team must be able to know where to go and what goals to achieve. The team needs to do the planning stage of the relevant vision, mission, to clear the goal clearly.

John R. Schermerhorn (2010: 377), argues that "A team of collection of people who interact interactively to pursue a common goal." The team as a group of people who interact to pursue common goals. The formation of a team when a number of people have the determination to achieve a common goal. Because the team is able to contribute greatly to a success in an organization. Mullins (2005: 519) "Teams occur when a number of people have common goals and recognizes that their personal success is dependent on the success of others". It is clear that teams are formed when a number of people share a common goal and recognize that personal success depends on the success of others in the team. The process of achieving a goal is an expectation and aspiration that is always everyone's dream, including a team in the organization. Colquitt (2009: 419) that "Teams process is a term that includes different teams that contribute to their ultimate end goals." Process teams are various types of activities and interactions that occur in teams that contribute to final destination. To achieve a final goal planned, it is necessary to have good cooperation, interdependence, communication and intensive interaction and

have the same vision and mission. Team management is based on the application of management functions, especially in planning and scheduling work, assigning of work tasks, training members, evaluating performance, and monitoring the quality of work. (quality control). Colquitt (2009: 376) division of teams in organizations includes: work teams (work teams), management teams (management teams), parallel teams (parallel teams), project teams (project teams), and action teams (action teams). The effectiveness of the team according to Robbins and Judge (2009: 362) "Effective teams have confidence in themselves. The believe they can succeed. "This means that an effective team has confidence in themselves, and is sure to succeed. An effective team in a variety of situations where individuals can do better work, just as they solve problems perfectly. McShane and Glinow (2008: 238) mention that "A team is effective when it benefits the organization, its members, and its own survival". It can be explained that the team is effective when it is beneficial to the organization and members for its survival. Edwar Sallis (2010: 188-190), argues that an effective team has several important factors, namely: (1) a team needs a clear member role, (2) the team needs clear objectives, (3) a team needs basic resources to operate, (4) a team needs to know the responsibilities and limits of its authority, (5) a team needs a work plan, (6) a team needs a set of rules to work, and (7) the team needs to develop a good team attitude and helpful. In team organizations are formed in various compositions and characteristics of the team. One important role of leadership in team formation is to design and manage teams to work effectively. As a team leader, it is very supportive to use the best method and decision making based on the problems and situations that occur. To achieve a goal in the team in a quality and timely manner, a commitment and good understanding is needed from the leaders and team members in the organization. Robbins and Judge (2009: 350) "Typically these tasks are planing and scheduling work, assigning tasks to members, making operating decisions, taking action on problems, and working with suppliers and costers. "Responsibilities in teams usually include planning and arranging work, assigning tasks to members, collective control of work steps, decision making operations, taking actions for various problems, and cooperation with suppliers and customers.

Sumber: Jason . A. Colquitt, A. Lepine & Michael J.Wesson, 2009

METHOD

This research was carried out at the Ternate City State Primary School in North Maluku Province. This research was carried out using a survey method with a quantitative approach. Data analysis techniques are carried out using path analysis (Path analysis). The method of collecting data needed in this study was carried out through a questionnaire that had been prepared in advance. This study will examine the relationship between research variables, and measure the influence of one variable with other variables. In this study there are three variables to be studied, namely organizational structure, procession and decision making. The hypothetical model of the study can be seen in the following figure:

Picture: 1. Hypothetical Research

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tests for data normality requirements were carried out using the Liliefors (L) test technique. The test criteria are data that is normally distributed if H_0 is accepted and not normally distributed if H_0 is rejected. H_0 is accepted if $L_{hitung} < L_{tabel}$ and H_0 are rejected if $L_{hitung} > L_{tabel}$.

Table 1 Summary of Analysis Results of Normality Test

No	Estimated Variable Error	N	L_{hitung}	L_{tabel}		Calculate
				$\alpha = 0,05$	$\alpha = 0,01$	
1	X_3 atas X_1	80	0,046	0,099	0,115	Normal
2	X_3 atas X_2	80	0,057	0,099	0,115	Normal
3	X_2 atas X_1	80	0,065	0,099	0,115	Normal

Significance and linearity tests are performed using the F test in the ANAVA table. Criteria for testing the significance of regression by comparing $F_{count} > F_{table}$ is significant. Whereas for the regression linearity test criteria by comparing $F_{count} < F_{table}$ then Linear.

Table 2 Significance Test and Linear

Regression	Regression Equation	TestSignification		Test Linearity Test		Ket
		F _{hitung}	F _{tabel = α = 0,01}	F _{hitung}	F _{tabel = α = 0,05}	
X3 atas X1	$X_3' = 64,834 + 0,427 X_1$	23,401**	3,964	0,929 ^{ns}	1,695	Significant
X3 atas X2	$X_3' = 76,468 + 0,325 X_2$	12,593**	3,964	0,908 ^{ns}	1,694	Significant
X2 atas X1	$X_2' = 65,784 + 0,359 X_1$	11,106**	3,964	0,927 ^{ns}	1,695	Significant

Test hypotheses using path analysis. The results of the path coefficient calculation that shows the influence between variables are: (1) the calculation results of the path coefficient obtained that the path coefficient value from X1 to X3 (p₃₁) is 0.398 with thitung = 3.385 and t table = 1.665 at the significance level of 0.05. This shows that the value of t count (3.385) > t table (1.665) which means that the path coefficient from X1 to X3 is very significant, (2) the results of the path coefficient calculation obtained that the path coefficient value from X2 to X3 (p₃₂) is 0.233 with thitung = 2,246 and t table = 1,665 at a significance level of 0.05. This shows that the value of t count (2,246) > t table (1,665) which means that the path coefficient from X2 to X3 is very significant, (3) the results of the calculation of path coefficients obtained that the path coefficient value from X1 to X2 (p₂₁) is 0.353 with thitung = 3,332 and t table = 1,665 at a significance level of 0,05. This shows that the value of t count (3.332) > t table (1.665) which means that the path coefficient from X1 to X2 is very significant.

Figure 2. Path Analysis Model

Table 1.1 Summary of Results of Testing Hypotheses

No	Direct Impact	Line coefficient t	t _{hitung}	t _{tabel} $\alpha = 0,05$	Decision	Conclusions
1	(X ₁) terhadap (X ₃)	0,398	3,385	1,665	Ho ditolak	Influential directpositive
2	(X ₂) terhadap (X ₃)	0,233	2,246	1,665	Ho ditolak	Influential directpositive
3	(X ₁) terhadap (X ₂)	0,353	3,332	1,665	Ho ditolak	Influential directpositive

DISCUSSION

Based on the literature review and previous empirical studies, the authors synthesize the problems found in the study of the influence of organizational structure and the process team on decision making. The results of the analysis of theoretical studies and empirical evidence can be described as follows:

1. Organizational structure Influencing Decision Making

The first hypothesis testing results concluded that the organizational structure (X₁) has a direct positive effect on decision making (X₃). The proposed hypothesis is accepted and very significant. This can be seen from the results of the calculation of statistical tests in which the path coefficient (p₃₁) obtained from X₁ to X₃ is 0.398 with $t_{hitung} = 3.385$ and $t_{tabel} = 1.665$ at 95% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). Based on the results of the study showed that the influence of organizational structure on decision making amounted to 23.10%. Thus, the findings in this study support the underlying theory that organizational structure has a direct positive effect on decision making. Gibson et. al (2006: 395) argues that "The processes by which they make choices are termed organization design, which means quite simple decisions and actions that result in organizational structure." A process carried out by the leadership in making choices for designing organization, and is a decision and action that results in an organizational structure. The organizational structure is essentially a leadership decision-making process in a structured division of labor. This is intended to achieve an integrated framework in order to divide tasks and coordinate the activities of members of the organization. A good organizational structure can be seen from internal order, relationships between individuals, interaction with the environment, job specifications, departmentalization, chain of command, range of control, centralization and formalization. The division of labor by the leader (manager), in accordance with the ability of his skills will encourage the employee to be able to carry out the work effectively and efficiently. While decision making is the way that is carried

out by a leader to solve a problem in order to achieve the expected goals, regarding how to divide the work, authority, division of departments, and formalization. Dafft (2010: 244), states that the relationship between organizational structure and decision making is: (1) the set of formal tasks assigned to individuals and departments, (2) formal reporting relationships, including lines of authority, decision responsibility, number of hierarchical levels, and span of managers' control, (3) the design of the system to ensure effective coordination of employees across the department. "The organizational structure is (1) divides formal tasks of individuals and departments, (2) formal reporting relationships including lines of authority, responsibility, decision making, number of hierarchical levels and control management, and (3) system design to ensure effective coordination of employees in the department. To design and structure the organization, leaders have a very strategic role in making a decision-making process to divide the work, tasks and responsibilities, patterns of coordination, communication, work flow, establish formal authority lines, and allocate resources within the organization. Robbins and Coulter (2009: 256) explain that: When managers develop or change an organization's structure, they are engaged in organizational design, a process that solves decision about six key elements: work specialization, departmentalization, chain of command, span of control, centralization and decentralization, and formalization. To compile or change the structure of an organization, the leadership is involved in organizational design, which is a process for decision making regarding six important elements which includes: work specialization, departmentalization, chain of command, range of control, centralization and decentralization and formalization. Leaders in placing employees must be in accordance with the abilities and skills, as well as the competencies of the members of the organization so that the "right man on the right place" is realized. This will certainly facilitate planning, organizing, directing and controlling a leader (manager), especially the headmaster. In the organizational structure is very influential on decision making. This clearly shows the role of leadership in decision making in relation to the division of labor, authority, division of departments, and the range of control. Invancevich, Konapaske, and Matteson (2008: 451) explain that there are four decisions taken by the leadership in the division of labor, authority, division of departments, and control range, namely: (1) managers decide how to share the overall task into successively smaller jobs. Managers share the total activities of the task into smaller sets of related activities. The effect of this decision is to define job in terms of specialized activities and responsibilities, (2) managers decide the bases by which to group the individual jobs. This decision is much like any other classification decision and it can result in groups containing jobs that are relatively homogeneous (alike) or heterogeneous (different), (3) managers decide the appropriate size of the group reporting to each superior. As we have already noted, this decision involves determining whether spans of control are relatively narrow or wide, (4) managers distribute authority among the jobs. The authority is the right to make decisions without being approved by managers and to exact obedience from designated other people. All jobs containing some degree of the right to make decision. Tim prescribed limits. It can be explained that, the first decision focuses on individual positions, the second and third decisions focus on the department or group of positions, and the fourth decision is the decision to consider the issue of delegating authority to the entire organizational structure. The results of this study indicate that the organizational structure focuses on the role of leaders (managers) in decision making for the division of labor and

coordination of activities between an organization. This is important in order to support the achievement of organizational goals. Based on empirical evidence, this finding shows that the organizational structure directly influences decision making.

2. Process Team Influences Decision Making

The second hypothesis in this study is the process team (X2) has a direct positive effect on decision making (X3). The proposed hypothesis is accepted and very significant. This can be seen from the results of statistical test calculations obtained that the path coefficient (β_{23}) from X2 to X3 is 0.233 with t count = 2.246 and t table = 1.665 at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. These results indicate that t count is greater than t table then reject H_0 so that there is a significant effect of the path coefficient of this variable. The existence of this direct influence indicates that an effective process team will increase decision-making effectiveness. Conversely, the decline in process team effectiveness results in a decrease in the effectiveness of decision making. Based on the results of the study indicate that the influence of the process team on decision making is shown by the determinant coefficient of 0.139, which means that the process team's contribution to the decision making effectiveness is 13.90%. Thus, the findings in this study support the underlying theory that the process team influences the effectiveness of decision making. The results of this study reinforce and reinforce the theoretical model framework developed by Colquitt, Lepine, and Wesson, which says that the organizational structure and process team are very influential on decision making. John R Schermerhorn (2011: 393) suggests that; Decision making is the process of making choices among alternative possible courses of action. it is one of the most important group processes. but it is also complicated by the fact that teams can make decisions in defferent ways and face special decision making challenges. Decision making is a process of choosing a choice program and alternative actions. In fact the team can make decisions by differentiating when faced with challenges specifically in the organization. The formation of a team in the target organization is to increase work participation in making decisions and carrying out work, with the aim of improving performance. The link between decision making in the team, Dafft (2010: 572) explains that "Teams are designed to increase the participation of workers in the decision making and the conduct of their jobs, with the goal of improving performance." The team was formed to increase worker participation in decision making and carrying out work, with the aim of improving performance. The formation of a team has individuals with technical expertise such as; solve problems, make decisions, and interpersonal abilities, as well as high abilities in terms of extraversion, agreement, caution and emotional stability. process team, requires communication and relationships, response and adjustment and high level coordination and arrangements. Baldwin, Bommer and Rubbin (2008: 257) suggested that; When they are effective, teams make better decision than individuals and greatly outperform their best members. But can generate higher productivity and more rapid in novation and creativity, especially for complex work. It can be explained that, the team makes better decisions than individuals. In the team also the members can produce higher and faster productivity in innovation and creativity, especially for complex work. Robbins and Judge (2009: 350) "Typically these tasks are planing and scheduling work, assigning tasks to members, making operating decisions, taking action on problems, and working with suppliers and costers."

Responsibilities in teams usually include planning and work arrangements , assigning tasks to members, collective control of work steps, decision making operations, taking actions for various problems, as well as cooperation with suppliers and customers. Based on empirical evidence, this finding shows that the process team is one of the most important variables and has a direct influence on decision making.

3. Organizational structure influences the process team The third hypothesis in this study is the organizational structure (X1) has a direct positive effect on the process team (X2).

This proposed hypothesis is accepted and very significant. This can be seen from the results of the calculation of the statistical test that the path coefficient (β_{21}) from X1 to X2 is 0.353 with t count = 3.332 and t table = 1.665 at 95% significance level or $\alpha = 0.05$. These results indicate that t count is greater than t table so reject H_0 so it can be concluded that there is a positive direct effect of the path coefficient of this variable. The direct influence of these two variables indicates that with an improved organizational structure will increase the effectiveness of the process team. Conversely, an unfavorable organizational structure results in the implementation of an ineffective process team. Based on the results of the study showed that the influence of the organizational structure on the process team is shown by the determinant coefficient of 0.125, which means that 12.5% of the process team is influenced by the good organizational structure. The results of this study are in line with the theoretical model developed by Colquitt, Lepine, and Wesson, emphasizing that the organizational structure and process team are two variables included in the organizational mechanism and group mechanism. This illustrates that the organizational structure directly affects the process team. John R. Schermerhorn (2010: 245) explains that; organization with team structure extensively use both permanent and temporary teams to solve problems, complete special projects and accomplish day to day tasks. a structure uses permanent and temporary cross-functional teams to improve lateral relations. It can be explained that an organization with a team structure extensively uses the team and temporary teams to solve the problem of special projects in full and complete tasks day by day. The team structure also uses permanent and temporary teams in cross-functional teams to improve work relationships. The relationship between organizational structure and the team can be explained by Dafft (2010: 255-256), in three approaches, namely: (1) teams in organizations cross-functional team, which consist of employees from various functional departments who are responsible to meet as a team and resolve mutual problems, (2) approach is to use permanent teams, groups of employees who are organized in a similar way to formal departments, (3) with a team-based structure, the entire organization is made up of horizontal teams that coordinate their work and work directly with customers to accomplish the organization's goals. First, the approach to using teamwork in an organization is through a cross-functional team consisting of team members from various functional departments and meeting as a team and solving common problems, second, using a parmanen team, a group of employees who are organized in the same way as the department formal, and third, with a team-based structure that is the whole organization is composed by horizontal teams that coordinate their work and work directly with customers to achieve organizational goals. The team can contribute greatly to the organization, especially in the organizational structure. Because the team team has an effort to work together, influence each other, the relationship of interaction between

people, have a commitment and have the determination to achieve a common goal. Robbins and judge (2009: 269) explain that: In a team-based structure, the entire organization is made up of work groups or teams that perform the organization's work. Needless to say, in a team-based structure, employee empowerment is crucial because there is no managerial authority from top to botton. Rather, employee teams are free to design work in the way they think is the best. However, the teams are held responsible for all work activities and performance results in their respective are also. In a team-based structure, the entire organization consists of work groups or teams that carry out the work of the organization. Of course, in a team-based structure, employee empowerment is very important because there is no managerial authority line that flows from top to bottom. Instead the employee teams are free to design the work in the way that is considered the best. But the teams must be responsible for all work activities and performance results in their respective fields. From the results above, it shows that the organizational structure has a direct effect on the process team.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the data analysis and discussion described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. There is a positive direct influence on organizational structure on decision making. This means that the better the school organizational structure, the more effective the decision of the principal will be. On the contrary, the organizational structure is not good, the more ineffective the decision making of the principal is. Therefore a good organizational structure is an important variable to improve the effectiveness of decision making.
2. There is a positive direct influence of the process team on decision making. This means that the better the implementation of the process team conducted by the principal, the more effective the decision of the principal will be. On the contrary, the less good the implementation of the process team conducted by the principal, the more ineffective the decision making of the principal.
3. There is a positive direct influence on the organizational structure of the process team. This means that the better the organizational structure, the better the process team will be. Conversely, the less good the organizational structure, the less good the process team will be.

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